

Potentials And Socio-Economic Impact of Cultural Festivals with Focus on Foods, Costumes and Souvenirs

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Abstract

This is an empirical study with data taken from the three major ethnic groups in Kogi state with focus on the socio-economic impact of cultural festivals through the sales of food, clothing/textiles and souvenirs during the festivals and the possibility of empowerment and poverty alleviation through the activities that take place. This motivates an investigation using Kogi, a culturally rich state of Nigeriawhich is currently trying to diversify and uplift her economy. Using observation, interviews, survey and focus group discussions of tourism operators and cultural brokers including visits to venues and examination of documentary materials. The paper identifies the common cuisines and food or cash crops available in the locality; The local materials/fabrics or textiles that could be showcased at these festivals, were also mentioned by the respondents. They (the respondents) also shed lights on the kinds of souvenirs available for sale or for take away. These ranged from locally made hand crafts to fabricated equipment from waste materials amongst others. Some of the concrete outcomes were highlighted. 342 respondents were surveyed and interviewed. The findings are interpreted in a descriptive manner, using concepts of significance. These concepts function into their normative representational and material dimensions. Tourism planners, it is found, could be more proactive in developing a diversified economy.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15160163>

The planning policy dilemma extends to policy objects, lack of facilities and infrastructures. Artisans in rural areas can be encouraged to be productive on their own terms. Far away communities can lend support to their culture? Thereby empowering themselves, impacting the societies. Solutions might be sought, it is argued, using a participatory approach to cultural festival hosting. From the findings, there is great potentials in cultural festivals in the study area.

Key words: *Potentials, impact, socio-economic, empowerment, poverty alleviation, food, textile*

INTRODUCTION

Nigerian festivals feature a variety of traditional foods, depending on the region and the occasion. **Food** is something good to eat! Food is anything, solid or liquid that we take into the body system for nourishment! Food is health and health is wealth; Like the common proverb or saying; one man's food is another man's poison, food differ from region to region and some foods are taken or required for health on a daily basis, while others are taken or served occasionally. Festival seasons are seasons for special foods! Among the major points of discuss is the foods served for or in festivals especially in Nigeria.As you know,without food, we die!Food, especially, in its raw state, can be sold as a source of income to individuals, the community or the nation at large!

Another point considered for this journal paper is the kind of **Textile** materials that are commonly used or sold during celebrations such as cultural festivals! Nigerian festivals showcase a vibrant array of textiles, reflecting the country's rich cultural heritage. Some of these textiles are used to create stunning attires for daily use and also for other occasions such as cultural festivals! The choice of textiles often depends on the type of festival, the region, (such as, North, South, East or West) and the cultural group. Nigerian festivals are a true celebration of

color, texture and creativity. Just as in the case of foods, Textiles and clothing are also a good source of income to individuals, community and the nation at large!

Also to be considered in this Journal are souvenirs, **Souvenirs** serve as a reminder of the festival experience and promote Nigerian culture. They can be sold at the daily markets or festival markets and can be given out as gifts to participants, guests or sponsors etcetera. A list of some souvenir ideas that can be sold or given out during or after Nigerian festivals will be provided in the course of this study! Some of these souvenirs can serve as brands or signature for the particular festival or the area!

Introduction

EKUECHI, EGUNGUN AND EGWU FESTIVAL

Over the years, these festivals of kogi people of Nigeria have drawn undue attention because of the energetic, physical activities that characterize its celebration. Little or no attention has been drawn to the festival as a festival with functional responsibilities to the society. This report explores the festivals to investigate the dynamics of the elements in a pure festive performance setting, and the functional relevance of the festival to the people in particular and the wider society in general. If the organizers take full advantage of modern cultural practice, the entire festivals have the potentials of becoming a major tourist attraction with meaningful economic and material benefits for the people

According to Ododo, S. (1987), the people are positively inclined, they see life as essentially well and good. The order of the universe is seen as benevolent and predictable. There is justice and constancy in its rules and regulations. This is why an average Ebiraland person would not hesitate to vehemently question any form of injustice with every resource at his disposal. This could be between him and her people or between foreigners. The quest for justice, if resisted, can sometimes degenerate to very distasteful physical approach (confrontation) which many have misinterpreted as vicious, wicked and hostile attributes of the people. This philosophy of life is further interwoven with their belief in the world of the unborn, the living and the dead. "The belief finds more visible expression in MASQUERADE Festivals which celebrates ancestral transmigration. In other words, the festival is ancestor worship. The dead elderly ones are

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

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believed to have only moved from the land of the living to a higher realm from where they constantly watch over their people in the world of the living. They take note of their wrong doings, travails and rate of progress. All these they address with positive intent when they transmigrate to the land of the living through the eku-masquerades that feature in these festivals. There are several of them (masquerades). They move individually from homestead to homestead felicitating with the people. They admonish them for the wrong doings of the past and warn against future wrongs, pray for a blissful New Year, prophesy good tidings, and harvest all manners of requests from the people with a promise to see them fulfilled. These requests are usually centered on the desire to have children, build houses, and generally to live a fulfilling life. In many cases, people find their requests answered before the next annual Festival. This explains why every homestead goes into elaborate preparation (clean environment, buy New dresses, cook special delicacies such as; pounded yam, bean bread (Ekuru), viand and provide drinks such as; palm wine and beer) to welcome home their ancestors during the festival. Further requests are made for fortification against the coming festival. (Ododo, S. 1987) The festivals are usually celebrated in December.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cultural festivals are seen as an important / significant part of tourism, attracting and building tourist image within and outside the communities (Susic & Darvic, 2012). Ekanayake and Lonng (2012) observed that cultural festivals can help to extend the range of tourist products and services that can in turn boost tourism development. Godfrey & Clarke, (2013); Okpoko and Okpoko, (2014) also share the same opinion. In the view of Chio and Sikara, (2012), there is a need for proper or adequate planning in order to improve the viability of resources. On the other hand, Ngoka (2014) believes that positioning, promotion, branding and marketing of destinations are very important. According to 2013 tourism policy, the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation are charged with the responsibility of promoting, marketing, planning and management of festivals and tourism destinations. Cultural festivals fosters community pride and encourages development. Gursoy et al., Fredline and Deery (2015). Anderson and Lundberg (2013) believe that cultural festivals can foster unity, poverty alleviation and increase empowerment. In the opinion of Ayeni, Ebohon and Bankole (2013), Society and culture can hardly be separated, and the benefits of cultural festivals are enormous and may include; employment, infrastructure development, foreign exchange earning amongst others. Allen et al., (2013) Okpoko, et al., 2013; and Holloway (2012) believes that community should be responsible for planning, which should include, advertisements and that the success of cultural festivals depend largely on planning and attendance. This also is the view of Liangi et al., (2015).

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15160163>

UNESCO (2012) and Olokesusi, (2012) says, poor perception, lack of awareness, inadequate publicity, negative media reports and the absence of adequate documentary evidence are hiding factors for effective hosting. Igbojekwe et al., (2014) believe that residents should be enthusiastic about hosting cultural festivals, and so awareness and patronage is very important. There is the potential for networking and creativity, introducing physical products and services are very important! (Wang, 2019) (harisnivas@gdrc.org (2017)

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK /EXPECTED OUTCOMES

Cultural Festivals’ Indigenous Foods, Textiles/Clothing and Souvenirs

Cultural Heritage Community Empowerment (CHCE) Framework

Cultural Preservation=====

Community Engagement=====

Economic Empowerment== {Food, Textile and Clothing; Other Sourvenirs}

Innovation and Modernization=====

Cultural Exchange and Education=CULTURAL FESTIVAL PRODUCTS

Tourism Development=====

Social Cohesion and Identity=====

Environmental Sustainability=====

A boost to health and physical exercise etcetera=====

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK / EXPECTED OUTCOMES

Indigenous Cultural Festival Products (ICFP) Framework

Received: 4 April 2025
Revised: 10 April 2025
Accepted: 27 April 2025
 Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15160163>

Community Engagement (CE)

Innovation and Adaptation (IA)

Recreation and Tourism

METHODOLOGY

The sampling of the communities is presented in the Table 3.1 below:

S/No.		Community	Population	Population Sample size	study sample size
1		Ebira (Okene)	320,260	384	57
2		Koton Karfe	115,900	382	57
3		Ogori	39,622	380	57
4		Okun (Kabba)	145,446	383	57
5		Idah	79,815	382	57
6		Ayangba	189,976	383	57
		Total		2,294	342

The study sample size of the overall location of study is 342 calculated from the total sample population of 2294 respondents. Determined through Krejcie and Morgan and a

purposive sample. To achieve the desired result of accurate sampling and analysis, the sample was 342 for the analysis taking several other factors into consideration. To avoid bias a number of samples of questionnaires administered to the six selected location of cultural festivals in Kogi State were considered, distributed and retrieved to arrive at the study sample figure of 342 as in the last column above: Each of the three masquerade festivals is representative of 2 communities in each ethnic group.

The case studies/site for this research is the egungun masquerade festival in Kabba-Bunnu Local government area /other Okun speaking areas of Kogi state and the Ekuechi masquerade festival of Okene (The Ebirá speaking people of Kogi State), and Egwu festival in Igala land. These three communities form the basis for this research

Historical sites and attractions include; the Obaro, Atta and Ohinoi palace and historic hills, lakes, rivers, and a host of others, as well as hotels and event centres, etcetera.

RESULTS OR OUTCOMES

Cultural Preservation

Economic Empowerment

Market Growth

Community Development

Sustainable Tourism and Recreation

Creativity

Poverty Alleviation

Physical exercise

Healthy Foods among others.

{Food, Textile and Clothing} These and more are the potentials inherent in these festivals

CUISINE / CULINARY / FOOD

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15160163>

Common dishes served generally during Nigerian festivals include the following:

1. Jollof Rice: A popular one-pot dish made with rice, tomatoes and spices
2. Suya: Grilled meat skewers, typically made with beef, chicken, or goat accompanied with rice, tomatoes pepper, potatoes and spices
3. Egusi soup: A thick soup made with ground melon seeds, vegetables, meat or fish, cray fish and oil.
4. Akara: Fried bean cakes, often served with pap (akamu) or garri by the side!
5. Moi Moi: Steamed bean pudding, wrapped in leaves (elemi meje – with the addition of eggs, liver fish and meat stock etcetera).
6. Pounded Yam: A staple dish made from boiled and pounded yams, often served with specialized soups
7. Eba: A thick paste made from cassava flour/garri, served with specialized soups.
8. Tuwo Shinkafa: A rice dish from the North, made with mashed rice and served with miyan kubewa (a sauce)
9. Fufu (a.k.a Apu) A thick paste made from fermented cassava flour (A dish common in the South East and South-South region of Nigeria).
10. Kunu: A sweet, milky drink made from millet or sorghum. With a variation known as, “aya kunu”
11. Zobo: A sweet fruity drink, made from hibiscus flowers

Some festivals also feature special dishes such as:

- Ofada Rice during the Ofada Festival in Ogun State

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15160163](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15160163)

- Ofe Owerri during the Ekpe Festival in Imo State and Oha soup in Enugu
- Banga Soup and starch during the Banga Festival in Delta State. Owo Sauce as well!
- Groundnut soup and imegi soup in Etsako
- These dishes are often prepared in large quantities and shared among festival attendees, symbolizing unity and communion.

The people of Kogi state are known to have delicacies which they serve at important occasions like naming, weddings, burials and at cultural festivals. A meal that is common to all is pounded yam eaten with variety of soups. Amala, locally made Semovita, Akara Baba atu (Ekuru), One pot red Oil Jollof, Eko elewe, etcetera.

In Kogi West, particularly amongst the Okun people, common soups include: Ora soup (ground dried okra) akuku and tankelekan soup (Jute seed) egusi soup Sakoro/ ishapa or Imegi soup. A popular snack is called aadun (fried beans with palm oil and salt or sugar) other snacks include itowo and gorigo (beni seed). The soups are cooked with dried fish, cray fish and smoked bush meat. Palm wine is also served.

In Kogi East gogo (Beni seed grinded with little or no oil) soup, egusi soup with lumps of abaro is served with Pounded Yam, smoked or fresh fish and/bush meat/ Goat meat. Palm wine and Kola nuts are also presented along with the meals. Palm oil, one pot red oil Jollof rice, Burukutu (Guinea corn/millet), Eko elewe, Akara eka, Ori

In Kogi Central, meals served include; Ekuru (steamed beans), Pounded yam and gorigo (Beni seed) soup with smoked fish or smoked bush meat. Palm wine is also served. Common

snacks include gorigo (Beni seed). In Ogori they serve “Ade” (a locally brewed wine) with light refreshments like biscuits, sweets, chewing gum, and sugar and kola nuts etcetera.

The properties and nutritional values of some of the most popular soup ingredients is a theme for further research.

COSTUME / DRESS

Here are some traditional textiles commonly used in Nigerian festivals:

1. Adire (Tie and Dye): A resist-dyeing technique used to create unique patterns on cotton fabric
2. Ankara: (Wax Print): A colorful, printed fabric common or popular for its bold designs and patterns
3. 3. Aso-Oke: A handwoven fabric, made from cotton and silk, often used for ceremonial attire.
4. Akwete: A traditional Igbo textile, made from cotton and silk, featuring intricate designs.
5. Ofi: (Igala, Okun, Igbira, Agbaja, Oworo, Yoruba and Ogori Cloth): A handwoven fabric known for its simple yet elegant design!
6. Kente cloth: (from Ghana, but also used to create intricate designs on cotton fabric.
7. Batik: A resist-dyeing technique used to create intricate designs on cotton fabric.
8. Shuku (Headties): Colorful scarves used to adorn the head, often made from cotton or silk

These textiles are used to create stunning attires for everyday use and for special occasions like festivals and events; they include:

- Traditional garments like, agbada, Skirt and blouse, Kaftan and Buba/ wrapper/Sokoto or Soro.
- Headgear like, crowns, turbans, caps and headties
- Accessories like, scarves, caps, bags, shoes and jewelries

These, showcase, creativity and innovation, empowerment and poverty alleviation!

Textiles that are common to the people of Kogi state include: Ofi, Asho oke and adire (tie and dye or Kampala). The people of Okun were known for the weaving and trade of aso ipo (a red textile used for the burial of the wealthy). The people in Kogi central were known for the weaving and trade of aso ofi and the making of masquerade dresses. The people in Kogi East also make local dresses for their masquerades and for burials. These cultural outfits are also made for special occasions by the people of Kogi state and this forms part of the souvenirs traded and sold

SOUVENIRS:

Below are some souvenir ideas that can be showcased or sold or given out during or after Nigerian festivals:

1. Traditional clothing and accessories (e.g. adire, Ankara, aso-oke, head-ties and caps)
2. Hand-made crafts (e.g. wood works or carvings, pottery, beads, baskets, brooms, atimokasa etcetera.
3. Local snacks and spices (e.g. groundnuts, plantain chips, suya, spices, Pepper)
4. Festival-themed memorabilia (e.g T-shirts, Posters, Keychains)

5. Traditional instruments (e.g. drums, flutes, Shekere, Gong, Bell, local guitar)
6. Nigerian Music: CDs or DVDs
7. Handmade Jewelry: e.g. (beads, cowries, Sea Shells, bronze)
8. Local artwork (e.g. Paintings, Sculptures, prints)
9. Festival Scented perfumes or essential Oils (e.g. Osun Osun, Udi)
10. Traditional beauty products; e.g. Shea butter, Coconut oil, Henna, Palm kernel Oil
11. Nigerian tea or coffee
12. Hand made bags, purses and Shoes
13. Wood or Bronze figurines
14. Festival themed books or pamphlets
15. Local wines like, Palm wine, Pito, Burukutu, Otin-eka and all such fermented fruits
16. Assortments of food stuff, like, Cassava, yams, rice etcetera.
17. Wara, Nunu, Fura Quindrimu, Milk, Kunu, Zobo.

These souvenirs serve as a reminder of the festival experience and promote Nigerian culture!

These includes; aso oke, Ofi, Adire, Tie and Dye, Kampala, brooms, locally woven baskets, hoes, cutlasses, Dane guns, Gun powders, Traps (locally fabricated), Abada, Achi red cap or native cap (Navy blue and white, black and white, Red), Local /curative herbs, smoked fish and Bush meat, Palm oil and a host of other food stuff.

During some of these festivals, consultation of native doctors also take place.

Taboos: Elders and Kings or their representatives, spiritual fathers and Local priests are the only ones permitted into the inner caucus.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15160163>

Arena: King's palace, Market, interior sites, community halls, Civic centre, cordoned shrine areas.

CONCLUSION

This piece has been carefully put together within the limit of available space and time and has room for further research. Adequate planning and implementation is necessary for all individual states to boost production and economic development. The festivals on their own have potentials of being developed into world class tourism standards and could host or accommodate so many other activities that would create funfair alongside tourism / economic development, and boost social cohesion, unity, integration, or interactions. It also has the potentials of enriching or developing the environment. There are interesting sites within and around. Opportunities abound for further development and social interactions. Tourism, exercise and recreations are necessary requirements to keep body and soul together, therefore, it is recommended for all and sundry.

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APPENDICES

Observation and survey or Questionnaires!

Descriptive analyses!

One sample t-test statistics and paired sample correlation statistics